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Contents

1	Introduction.....	4
2	Basic biology of the impact of light.....	4
3	Modulations by biological factors	5
3.1	Sex differences.....	5
3.2	Lifespan changes	6
3.3	Diseases as a readout of the mechanisms of light actions.....	7
3.4	Interaction with other biological factors.....	9
4	Manipulation of light characteristics to unravel underlying mechanisms.....	9
4.1	Spectral tuning of light.....	9
4.2	Light dose-response.....	10
4.3	Prior light history.....	10
4.4	Spatial integration of light	11
5	What should be the next steps?.....	11
	References.....	12

1 Introduction

In this integrative report, we focus on the mechanisms studied in the LIGHTCAP project and the knowledge gained, or yet to be learned from the remaining analyses. Many projects are still ongoing, meaning that in most cases only preliminary conclusions can be drawn at this stage. For further details and references, the reader is referred to the published and forthcoming manuscripts of the individual ESRs. The purpose of this deliverable is merely to outline at a high-level the directions and interrelationships of the numerous studies – both completed and ongoing – in LIGHTCAP.

Following a presentation of the insights gained on the biological mechanisms of the non-image forming (NIF) impact of light, we present sources of modulation or variation of these mechanisms arising from i) biological factors and interaction between biological factors – ageing, disease, stress, arousal – and ii) light characteristics. We end the report with a description of what we consider to be the most urgent knowledge gaps about the mechanisms of action of light that need to be addressed in the future.

2 Basic biology of the impact of light

Several projects used objective measurements rather than subjective reports to unravel biological mechanisms. They focused on the activity and functional connectivity of the brain using **fMRI** (ESR03, ESR04), on **pupillometry** (ESR03, ESR04, ESR06) as a direct readout of the impact of light on the brain, on neuronal responsiveness using **TMS-EEG** (ESR04), on brain waves as markers of attention, alertness and sleepiness using **EEG** (ESR07), on **actimetry** (ESR05, ESR06) as a readout of rest-activity regulation, and on **melatonin** suppression (ESR05, ESR06, ESR10, ESR11) as one of the well-established measures for the impact of light. The studies also included **behavioural measures** that can be linked to the biological mechanism uncovered.

The impact of light on the brain can initially be seen as **changes in regional brain activity and in the crosstalk between brain regions, or connectivity**. The regions involved in the non-visual pathway of light are fairly well established in animal studies, but the translation to humans is not straightforward and it requires further investigation. When it comes to non-visual effects of light, the hypothalamus is one of the main regions of interest because of the dense direct inputs it receives from ipRGCs. Fermin Balda (ESR03) and Roya Sharifpour (ESR04) focused on different subparts of the hypothalamus and how they respond to light. Their preliminary results suggest that posterior subparts of the hypothalamus are modulated by illuminance across different cognitive tasks including attention, working memory and emotion. In contrast, their preliminary results suggest a deactivation of the anterior hypothalamus when no cognitive task is performed. In addition, the connectivity between subcortical regions is affected by light. Following a first report showing that the thalamus influences the parietal cortex when exposed to blue-enriched light during an attentional task (Paparella et al., 2023), current analyses aim to extend the investigation

to a potential dose-dependent relationship with the connectivity between the thalamus and the cortex. Future analyses will also examine the connectivity between the anterior and posterior hypothalamus.

Considering the brain from its electrophysiological properties, Elifnaz Gecer (ESR07) has also focused on brain physiology. She systematically assessed light-induced modulations in brain activity, employing a high temporal, spatial and spectral resolution to study the effects of light on EEG power densities. Her preliminary results indicate that different EEG oscillatory modes are affected by light intensity, contrasting two metameric light conditions and a dim control condition. Oscillations in the Beta band (16-30 Hz) were affected within the first minute of light exposure, whereas alpha (8-12 Hz) and theta (4-8 Hz) responded within the 10 minutes of the exposure. Similar to the MRI signal, EEG measures were affected by light – albeit modest - while behaviour did not show significant changes, suggesting that EEG (and fMRI) measures are more sensitive to changes in light than the performance measures and subjective alertness ratings. Still based on electrophysiology, Roya Sharifpour (ESR04) also focuses on **cortical excitability** as an objective basic measure of brain function known to be modulated by the interaction of sleep homeostasis and circadian processes. Preliminary results show that the effect of light on cortical excitability is not immediately obvious and depends on several sources of variability, which will be discussed in the next sections.

Overall, the current preliminary findings from the fMRI and EEG studies provide evidence that light can affect cognitive brain function before it translates into detectable behavioural responses, and give us insights into the sensitivities of the different methods.

In a field study, Rafael Lazar (ESR06) looked at the **pupil light reflex** as another indicator of light mechanisms. In line with the EEG investigation of ESR07, the results confirm the rapid effect of light on brain function, i.e., within seconds.

3 Modulations by biological factors

Light signals reach the brain through the photoreceptors of the retina mentioned in Section 1. Rather than focusing on visual perception, the studies that have looked at the biology of the brain to gain insight into the mechanism of light effects have focused on the non-visual effects of light on sleep, attention, alertness, mood, pupillary response, etc.

3.1 Sex differences

Although they are part of many of the planned investigations in the LIGHTCAP project, sex differences are mostly of secondary interest. With the exception of preliminary results from the cortical excitability study (ESR04), there is little evidence to date. Although the mechanisms are uncertain, teenage females seemed to have a greater effect of light on their cortical excitability. If confirmed, this could mean that both early age and sex affect the mechanism underlying light impact. Further evidence for a sex-dependent NIF effect of light in humans comes from Fatemeh

Fazlali (ESR05), who found in an exploratory analysis that melatonin suppression during exposure to moderate light levels was stronger in females than in males. Richard Jedon (ESR09) 's ongoing analyses indicate that sex may also play a role in the impact of light on the perception of safety, though potentially through difference in (trait) anxiety. Further analyses will bring important insight on how sex differences shape the mechanisms of light impact.

3.2 Lifespan changes

We have learned more about the main mechanisms of NIF effects of light, but it is also important to note that the biology of the brain and of our entire organism changes with age. The effects of light on different age groups are different. Teenagers on one hand are still in the stage of development and they may be more sensitive to changes in light. Their pupils are larger and their lens is more transparent than in older individuals. Biologically, they are also later chronotypes, which in combination with early school hours and strong late-night screen habits, puts them in a potentially vulnerable position. In our project, we investigated the differences in the brains of teenagers compared to adults at different light settings as well as their pupillary responses. Beyond the development of teenagers, biology continues to change across the lifespan up into late adulthood. We see these changes in smaller pupil sizes, yellowing of the lens of the eye as well as the changes in the count and distribution of certain photoreceptors in the retina. While the literature already points to differences in some of these physical aspects, it is still unclear how the response to light of the underlying neural structures is affected by age.

For **teenagers** LIGHTCAP researchers wondered how different levels of light translate into NIF effects in wakefulness and sleep, and how they are modulated by other aspects such as time of day or sex. In an fMRI study with different light levels, Roya Sharifpour (ESR04) investigates whether teenagers' brains are more responsive to the changes in light. This study will test the hypothesis that light first reaches subcortical structures and then gradually affects cortical regions as the dose of light increases. Preliminary findings indicate that there seems to be a strong time-of-the-day effect for the connectivity metric. The ongoing analyses seem to indicate that teenagers may present a different impact of light on their subcortical areas when compared to younger adults. These changes seem to be translated into changes in cortical excitability, particularly in teenage females (see above). Complementing this research, Rafael Lazar (ESR06) is investigating the effects of light on the physiology of adolescents. Although the data collection has been completed, the analyses have not yet begun, but are ongoing and will hopefully provide valuable insights into the extent to which previous light history influences late-night NIF effects in adolescents in the near future.

A field study conducted by Rafael Lazar (ESR06) on individuals with a wide range of ages, from 18 to 87, investigated the role of age on the pupil responses (Lazar et al. 2024). In this study, participants were able to move dynamically in and out of indoor and outdoor environments. The study successfully confirmed the three hypotheses: firstly, it showed that light affects pupil size in the field in a dose-dependent manner; secondly, it demonstrated that ageing reduces pupil size; and,

lastly, it indicated that melanopic units are better predictors of this effect than the photopic units. Importantly, the effect of ageing on pupil size was more pronounced at lower light levels, suggesting that the mechanism is most altered at lower illuminances.

In another fMRI study currently in the data acquisition phase, led by Fermin Balda (ESR03), the LIGHTCAP project is testing whether several subcortical regions thought to be involved in the NIF pathway in the brain, such as the hypothalamus, thalamus and locus coeruleus, are less affected by light in the older adults. Overall, these studies will assess how the sensitivity to light changes as a function of age, and will point towards potential compensatory mechanisms at play.

Finally, we complement our laboratory research into the effects of light on older people with a closer look at **care facilities**. In a real-time field study conducted by Megan Danell (ESR14), we explored the relationships between the light exposure and sleep-wake patterns as measured by actimetry. We learned that although the orientation of their room in the facility influenced the amount of light potentially available to the residents, it was largely their behaviour that determined their light exposure. This study further suggests that there is a correlation between average light exposure, time spent above threshold (200 lx) by residents and daytime napping. The sample size of this study was, however, limited due to the special condition of its patients making it difficult to draw causal conclusions. In another study, Megan Danell (ESR14) aimed at extending the investigation to people with dementia and used biodynamic lighting to affect physiology. However, from what we know so far, the lights were not bright enough to evoke non-imagery responses and cause behavioural changes..

Overall, these studies are key to demonstrating our current understanding of the mechanism through which light impacts humans across the lifespan, and combined with the results that we will soon obtain from the studies currently in the acquisition/analysis phase we will have a better idea of how to translate them into applications.

3.3 Diseases as a readout of the mechanisms of light actions

In this project, we explored the multifaceted relationships between light and health but also between light and diseases. We investigated the impact of light exposure on retinal and brain impairment as well as sleep disorders.

Retinitis pigmentosa (RP) is a genetic retinal disease characterised by the progressive degeneration of photoreceptor cells which leads to gradual visual loss and potentially causes severe visual impairment over time. Ashwathi Prithviraj (ESR02) was interested in studying how melanopsin function changes over the course of the retinal degeneration to foster our understanding of this disease and help advise future interventions. For this we have generated a mouse model of RP with human red cone knocked in to help in silent substitution studies (a method which can isolate light responses of different photoreceptors). Previous studies have, however, shown that the

degeneration of the retina can be slowed down in this model by housing the mice under constant darkness since birth. This is an unnatural condition to house the mice as light is very important in the development of the visual system. So, we initiated the investigation of RP by testing whether the Outer nuclear layer (ONL) of the retina was preserved when the mice were housed under dim red light compared to complete darkness. In the red cone knocking mice this red light is sufficient to support vision, but we reasoned that it would not induce degeneration (which is initiated by photoactivation of rods). We indeed show that the ONL was similarly preserved under both conditions till at least 2 months of age validating the red light approach. Studies are currently ongoing to track the changes in melanopsin function at early, mid and late stages of this disease using electrophysiology.

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a progressive neurological disorder that primarily causes insidious deterioration of brain functions, leading to cognitive decline and memory loss. AD is also characterised by sleep and circadian rhythm dysfunction. Bright light exposure has been well studied to help in improving sleep and circadian disruption in human studies. Ashwathi Prithviraj (ESR02) has also explored whether exposure to bright daytime light could similarly have a therapeutic effect in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease (AD) and help ameliorate the disease pathology. AD mice and control mice were housed long-term under either dim or bright daytime light conditions and tested over a period of 4 months to track the progression of the disease using OCT retinal scans, behavioural tests, circadian activity and pathology, to test whether the light treatment had any effect. At a pre-symptomatic stage, current analyses reveal no significant difference in retinal degeneration and behavioural cognition in AD mice between repeated exposed to bright light or housed under dim light conditions.

Light may indirectly affect sleep-wake regulation through its influence on circadian rhythms. Whether sleep disorders caused by a physical condition (e.g. sleep apnoea and narcolepsy) also influence the NIF effects of light, or vice versa, is unclear.. Vaida Verhoef (ESR08) addressed this question. She, however, argued that individual daytime complaints (such as sleepiness) from patients suffering from sleep apnea and narcolepsy needed to be better characterised first, as she realised that complains were somewhat inconsistent with the most common diagnostic metrics. Indeed, while the metrics showed variations following sleep restriction (as compared to a well-rested condition), they failed to capture the cumulative effect of multiple sleep restrictions (found in previous studies). Interestingly, patients highlighted interesting time-of-day changes in their complaints that were successfully detected by the scales and should be considered in scientific studies. The next study aims at observing such time-dependent effect of sleepiness more objectively among persons experiencing restricted sleep on a regular basis (i.e., young parents). Additionally, this study investigates through which mechanisms light exposure may affect daily variation in the daytime complaints these persons experience.

3.4 Interaction with other biological factors.

Lighting in **outdoor environments** and its impact on **safety** was investigated in the LIGHTCAP project by three SRs fellows: Richard Jedon (ESR09), Aysheh Alshdaifat (ESR10) and Nima Hafezparast Moadab (ESR11). This focus on safety can be divided into two parts: the feeling of safety (e.g., walking alone at night) and “objective” safety (e.g. preventing accidents while driving or falls while walking).

One potential mechanism behind the general feeling of safety or safety perception is related to anxiety: if you do not feel anxious, it means you feel safe. Anxiety can be influenced by lighting conditions as well as other factors (e.g. trait anxiety). Vice versa, one’s anxiety or arousal level may influence the minimum required light level to feel safe in outdoor situations. Richard (ESR09) has conducted several studies to investigate these bidirectional and multifaceted relationships. In contrast, our research on objective safety, in terms of preventing car accidents, shows that it is related to inattention due to distraction or to alertness. Alertness, in turn, is impaired in situations of high sleepiness, which are related to the circadian timing system and sleep-wake homeostatic mechanisms. Our research indicates that the short-wavelength light improve saccadic eye movements and attentional disengagement, facilitate cognitive flexibility and improve performance on cognitive tasks (ESR10 & ESR11). In some instances, light exposure was superior to caffeine in sustaining performance. Light mechanisms of action are therefore at play in real-life situations. Safety is, however, also dependent on perception of hazards and the light levels required to improve cognition were accompanied by a decrease in perceptual performance, which should prevail in driving situations.

4 Manipulation of light characteristics to unravel underlying mechanisms

Many investigations of the LIGHTCAP project have involved manipulating the properties of light to better understand its mechanisms of action. In particular, identifying which of the photoreceptors, or a combination of them, is the main driver of the multiple effects of light is an important step towards understanding how light interacts with the brain. In the following sections, we will separate these manipulations and provide a rationale for selecting these in particular to advance our understanding of the underlying mechanisms of the effects of light on cognition, attention, and perception. The light(ing) manipulations used to unravel the underlying mechanisms are classified according to the light characteristics targeted: spectral, spatial, and temporal distribution of light and its dose or intensity. As in the previous section, manipulations of light characteristics were related to behavioural measures.

4.1 Spectral tuning of light

Retinal photoreceptors present different sensitivities to photon wavelengths. Several ESRs manipulated the spectral composition of light to target specific sets of photoreceptors (i.e., cones

or ipRGCs) to gain a better understanding of the contributions of these photoreceptors to the impact of light. They all focused on the acute (i.e., direct) effects of light on alertness and cognition during the daytime or evening/nighttime. Fatemeh Fazlali (ESR05) studied how cone-driven responses to light affect alertness and melatonin suppression using the silent substitution method, which consists of using different light spectra that lead to similar ipRGC activation, while leading to different stimulation of in s-cones, m-cones or l-cones. In contrast, Fermin Balda (ESR03) and Elifnaz Geçer (ESR07) targeted ipRGC activation by metameric lighting to contrast conditions with high vs. low melanopic activation while keeping cone stimulation constant (planned for ESR03, not completed yet). Roya Sharifpour (ESR04) also manipulated the spectral composition of the light to produce differences in melanopic illuminance and studied the impact of these lighting conditions on modulations in specific subcortical regions of the brain related to the completion of attentional, working memory, and emotional processes. Analyses of all these studies are still ongoing and preliminary results are still limited. We expect that these studies will provide important information on how cones and ipRGCs contribute to the modulation of alertness, cognition and brain function.

4.2 Light dose-response

It has been well established that for several non-visual outcomes, light affects the human brain and behaviour in a dose-dependent manner, meaning that higher light intensity and duration can elicit a larger effect. However, these dose-response relationships may differ among outcome parameters and between daytime and nighttime. To gain more insight into the visual and non-visual integration of different light intensities across different methods, several ESRs (ESR02, ESR03, ESR04, ESR06, ESR07, ESR10, ESR11, ESR13, ESR14) have applied light interventions in various steps of intensities. Evidence from several of these studies suggests that NIF responses to light are indeed integrated in a dose-dependent manner both during the day and at night. These include neural activation at both subcortical and cortical levels, several physiological parameters such as pupil size and melatonin suppression, test performance in reaction time, as well as subjective reports of sleepiness. Interestingly, in outdoor situations, road lighting can only affect pedestrian alertness in the evening if the illuminance at the eye reaches 100 lx, meaning that typical outdoor lighting level (2 lx to 20 lx) does not seem to recruit the mechanism of light impact of non-visual function (ESR10 & ESR11). Further insights into the dose-dependent integration of light processing in humans will be provided in forthcoming analyses of the ongoing studies.

4.3 Prior light history

In particular a project, led by Rafael Lazar (ESR06), manipulated light over time to assess whether different levels of afternoon light would increase or decrease responsiveness to evening lighting conditions. Assessment of light-induced sleepiness and melatonin suppression was one of the tools used by LIGHTCAP ESRs to address this question. Analyses are ongoing, but we expect to see results on how the dose of prior light affects sleep through the amount of EEG delta power density and changes in sleep architecture.

4.4 Spatial integration of light

The spatial distribution and direction of light are critical for describing light environments and essential features of natural conditions. How does the light processing system integrate this spatial information from the light environment? The LIGHTCAP consortium has addressed this question in both mice and humans. Qian Huang (ESR01) investigated how vertical patterns in visual scenes alter behavioural states in rodents by studying preferences for one scene over the other in a forced-choice paradigm. To investigate whether melanopsin plays a mechanistic role in this ability of mice to distinguish environments based upon the spatial distribution of light, Qian conducted her behavioural experiments in a wild-type and a transgenic mouse model (melanopsin knockout mice), manipulating the distribution of light in the vertical plane while keeping the other properties of light constant. The results of their study suggest that low-frequency vertical patterns affect the behavioural preferences of mice through a melanopsin-dependent pathway. Vertical patterns of visual scenes altered the rodents' behavioural states, with the difference in radiance around the horizon playing a major role in the wild-type mice's preference choices. Preferences were disturbed in the melanopsin knockout mice.

Nikodem Derengowski (ESR12) on the other hand investigated how the spatial distribution of light affects human participants' alertness during daytime by manipulating the directionality of the light. To gain insight into the mechanisms of spatial integration, he tested light coming from different parts of the visual field, thus affecting different locations on the retina, while keeping the vertical illuminance at the eye homogeneous. The results of the study suggest that light from the upper part of the visual field was more effective in reducing subjective sleepiness and improving reaction time performance. These results, which will be part of yet to be published articles, suggest that in humans light from 'above', which stimulates the lower part of the retina, is weighted more strongly in the light-induced effects on alertness. Regarding the spatial distribution of personal light exposure in general, Steffen Hartmeyer (ESR13) also showed how much this distribution varies across different environments, activities and over time. This raises the question how these findings may translate to the real-world, and how the spatial effects of light exposure may integrate over time in daily life.

5 What should be the next steps?

Complete the photoreceptor story! Determine the contribution of each photoreceptor type to the impact of light by controlled light manipulations. Metameric lights via the silent substitution method should be favoured to address this issue.

Go beyond blue light! Consider other wavelengths, as there is preliminary evidence for behavioural effects of light, even composed of slightly shorter wavelengths than in the blue range. In this regard, subjects' prior expectations of what a particular light colour/wavelength might do should be carefully controlled and recorded.

Widen the age range, particularly downwards! Much remains to be understood about the specific impact of light on infants, children and early teens. Preliminary evidence in the literature suggests that there may be specificities.

Increase power! Light impact may sometimes lead to small effects. This may not mean that they are not important but they should be approached with the right sensitivity. Larger sample size should be privileged in the future.

Consider the gaze of the animal! LIGHTCAP considered gaze position in humans as a potential source of variation in the impact of light and it appears that for indoor desk-type condition, it may not be an important factor. Studies in animals should also assess whether a similar statement can be drawn in animals and assess how much it may affect investigation of the mechanisms at stake.

Get out in the field! In-lab controlled conditions are ideal means for establishing mechanisms. These mechanisms need to be tested in the field. New devices and portable equipment allow the test of mechanisms in more ecological conditions (e.g. ambulatory pupillometry, EEG, videos). Higher temporal resolution should be preferred in the real world, where conditions are constantly changing.

Integrate several theoretical frameworks in the design of the experiments! Beyond biology and physiology, light mechanisms are influenced by many sociological and psychological factors that are still overlooked, and it would be highly valuable to integrate them in research projects (e.g. for safety studies).

Elucidate individual differences! In line with the previous point, the simultaneous acquisitions of multiple measurements, e.g. combine melatonin with EEG, combine brain and eye measures, collect data on prior light history. This will contribute to a better apprehension of interindividual differences in the impact of light.

Consider disorders and diseases! Applying the insights on the mechanism underlying light's impact, including in ageing, to disorders such as neurodegenerative diseases, sleep disorders and mood disorders is necessary for the true application of light.

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